

Spatially Explicit Graph Neural Networks for Epidemic Forecasting: Evidence from Socioeconomic Embeddings

Fengjiao Li*, Meiliu Wu*, and Anahid Basiri*

*School of Geographical and Earth Sciences, University of Glasgow, Glasgow, UK,
f.li.3@research.gla.ac.uk, meiliu.wu@glasgow.ac.uk, ana.basiri@glasgow.ac.uk

Abstract

Graph neural network models have shown strong performance in epidemic forecasting by encoding spatial interactions, yet socioeconomic heterogeneity at the node level remains underexplored. Building on previous work on spatial graph design, this study examines whether learned socioeconomic representations can improve forecasting under fixed spatial interaction structures. We propose a framework in which node embeddings are learned from static socioeconomic attributes using a graph convolutional network and then incorporated into a diffusion convolutional recurrent neural network. Three input configurations are evaluated in Glasgow and Edinburgh: historical infection rates only, infection rates with raw socioeconomic attributes, and infection rates with learned node embeddings. Results show that the contribution of node embeddings is context dependent. In Glasgow, embeddings mainly improve relative error, whereas in Edinburgh they improve both relative and absolute error. These findings highlight the value of context sensitive node representations in epidemic forecasting.

Keywords: GeoAI, Spatially Explicit AI, Graph Neural Networks, Node Embeddings, Spatio-temporal Epidemic Forecasting.

1. Introduction

Accurate spatio temporal forecasting of infectious diseases is essential for public health planning, particularly in urban settings, where dense populations, heterogeneous socioeconomic structures, and large scale human mobility interact to shape complex transmission dynamics (Kraemer et al. 2020; Bamba et al. 2020). These urban specific processes challenge conventional forecasting approaches and motivate models that explicitly capture structured spatial interactions. Although geographic space is inherently continuous, the forecasting problem considered here is defined over discrete areal units, for which both observations and prediction targets are reported at the area level. In this setting, graph based models provide an appropriate operational representation, with

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nodes corresponding to spatial units and edges encoding spatial relations through which epidemic influence may propagate. Spatially explicit graph neural networks (GNNs) have therefore become a useful framework for modelling such non Euclidean spatial dependence and have shown strong performance across traffic, epidemic, and environmental forecasting tasks (Li et al. 2018; Deng, Rangwala, and Ning 2020; Ding et al. 2023).

Recent studies show that epidemic forecasting performance is highly sensitive to spatial graph construction. GNN based models that encode geographic proximity and human mobility outperform non graph baselines (Nguyen et al. 2023; Xie et al. 2022; Zheng et al. 2024), highlighting the importance of spatial interaction design. Li et al. further demonstrate that the effectiveness of mobility informed graphs is strongly city dependent: mobility enhanced graphs improve predictions in Glasgow, whereas purely geographic adjacency performs better in Edinburgh (Li, Wu, and Basiri 2025). This suggests that no single link level representation is universally optimal and that improving edge structure alone may be insufficient.

Meanwhile, epidemiological studies consistently show that socioeconomic factors such as age structure, income, employment, and housing shape infection risk and outcomes (Bambra et al. 2020). However, such node level heterogeneity is rarely encoded explicitly in GNN based epidemic forecasting models, limiting interpretability and generalisability. To address this gap, we examine whether learned socioeconomic node representations can improve forecasting under fixed spatial interaction structures. Specifically, we learn node embeddings from static socioeconomic attributes under fixed graph constraints and integrate them into the forecasting model to assess their contribution across cities with contrasting interaction patterns. By distinguishing between link level spatial interaction design and node level socioeconomic representation, this study provides new insight into how urban spatial and social structure jointly shape epidemic predictability.

2. Methods

2.1 Problem Setting

Let a city be partitioned into N spatial zones, each represented as a node in a graph. For each spatial zone i (interzone), we observe a univariate epidemic time series $y_{i,t}$ (infection rate) and a vector of static socioeconomic attributes, including population aged 0–15 and 65+, gender, income, employment, and housing conditions. The epidemic time series provide the dynamic signal for short term forecasting, whereas the socioeconomic attributes provide relatively stable contextual information that characterises persistent differences between areas. Our objective is to predict future infection rates over a short term horizon $H = 7$ given the historical observations and spatial context:

$$\hat{\mathbf{Y}}_{t+1:t+H} = f_{\theta}(\mathbf{Y}_{t-L:t}, \mathbf{Z}, \mathcal{G}), \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{Y}_{t-L:t}$ denotes the past $L = 7$ time steps, \mathcal{G} is a spatial interaction graph, and $\mathbf{Z} \in R^{N \times d}$ is a matrix of node embeddings learned from socioeconomic attributes and spatial structure.

2.2 Graph Construction

We adopt the spatial graph constructions proposed in our previous work to represent different mechanisms of interzone connectivity. Specifically, we consider single graphs derived from geographic adjacency, road network proximity, or human mobility flows, as well as hybrid graphs formed by linearly combining mobility with geographic or road based adjacency using a mixing parameter $\alpha \in [0, 1]$. Each spatial graph is represented by a weighted adjacency matrix \mathbf{W} . All formal definitions and implementation details are identical to those in (Li, Wu, and Basiri 2025).

2.3 GNN based Node Embedding Learning

We deliberately disentangle node level and link level representations using a two stage design. Node embeddings are learned under a fixed spatial interaction graph and are not explicitly optimised for forecasting, allowing us to isolate the contribution of socioeconomic information while keeping the link configuration in the DCRNN unchanged. This design also reflects the distinct roles of the two input types: the epidemic time series capture temporal variation, whereas the socioeconomic attributes provide quasi static contextual information about each area. End to end optimisation would entangle node and link effects and hinder attribution to node level heterogeneity.

Node embeddings are learned using the same spatial graph as the one used in the forecasting model, ensuring that all comparisons isolate the effect of node level representations rather than differences in spatial connectivity. For node embedding learning, we adopt symmetric normalisation of the adjacency matrix,

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}} = \mathbf{D}^{-\frac{1}{2}}(\mathbf{W} + \mathbf{I})\mathbf{D}^{-\frac{1}{2}}, \quad (2)$$

which is standard in graph convolutional networks and ensures numerically stable feature propagation.

GCN propagation. Let $\mathbf{H}^{(0)} = \mathbf{X}$ denote the input feature matrix. Each GCN layer is defined as:

$$\mathbf{H}^{(l+1)} = \sigma\left(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{H}^{(l)}\mathbf{W}^{(l)}\right), \quad (3)$$

where $\sigma(\cdot)$ is the ReLU activation function. After K layers, the final node embeddings are obtained as:

$$\mathbf{Z} = \mathbf{H}^{(K)} \in R^{N \times d}. \quad (4)$$

The embedding of node i is given by the i th row of \mathbf{Z} , denoted as $\mathbf{e}_i \in R^d$.

Graph smoothness regularisation. To encourage spatial coherence, we impose a graph smoothness constraint:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{smooth}} = \frac{1}{N} \text{tr}(\mathbf{Z}^\top \mathbf{L} \mathbf{Z}), \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{L} = \mathbf{D} - \mathbf{W}$ is the graph Laplacian constructed from the raw adjacency matrix.

Stability regularisation. To improve robustness to noise in socioeconomic inputs, we apply an input perturbation stability constraint:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{stab}} = E_{\epsilon} [\|f_{\text{GCN}}(\mathbf{X}) - f_{\text{GCN}}(\mathbf{X} + \epsilon)\|_2^2], \quad \epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2). \quad (6)$$

Embedding objective. The overall embedding learning objective is:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{embed}} = \lambda_1 \mathcal{L}_{\text{smooth}} + \lambda_2 \mathcal{L}_{\text{stab}}, \quad (7)$$

where λ_1 and λ_2 control the strength of spatial smoothness and stability regularisation, respectively.

Figure 1: Overview of the proposed framework. We compare three input configurations: (1) infection rate only, (2) infection rate with raw socioeconomic features, and (3) infection rate with learned node embeddings. Node embeddings are learned from socioeconomic attributes under a fixed spatial interaction graph and concatenated with temporal inputs. All configurations are evaluated using the same DCRNN model with an identical spatial graph (Li et al. 2018), thereby isolating the effect of node level representations.

2.4 Input Configurations for DCRNN

The three input configurations are designed to distinguish the contribution of temporal information from that of socioeconomic context. In all cases, the infection rate series remains the primary temporal input to the forecasting model. The socioeconomic variables, whether used directly or through learned node embeddings, are included as contextual node level information rather than as additional temporal signals. This allows us to assess whether richer area representations improve forecasting under the same spatial interaction structure.

Baseline. Only the historical infection rate is used as input:

$$\mathbf{x}_{i,t} = y_{i,t}.$$

Raw features. The input is formed by concatenating the infection rate with the normalized socioeconomic attributes:

$$\mathbf{x}_{i,t} = [y_{i,t}, \mathbf{x}_i^\top]^\top.$$

Node embedding features. The infection rate is concatenated with the learned node embedding:

$$\mathbf{x}_{i,t} = [y_{i,t}, \tilde{\mathbf{e}}_i^\top]^\top,$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{e}}_i \in R^d$ is the normalized node embedding.

3 Results and Analysis

This study focuses on Glasgow and Edinburgh, two major Scottish cities with distinct demographic and mobility patterns. We use datasets: (1) daily COVID-19 infection data aggregated at the InterZone level¹, (2) population mobility data describing interzone flows², (3) road and rail network data derived from OpenStreetMap³, and (4) socioeconomic and demographic data from the Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation⁴.

3.1 Glasgow

Building on our previous analysis of spatial graph design (Li, Wu, and Basiri 2025), we adopt a mixed spatial graph for Glasgow that combines mobility flows (60%) and geographic adjacency (40%). This configuration consistently achieved the strongest forecasting performance on the validation set and is therefore treated as the baseline spatial structure in the following experiments.

Table 1 compares forecasting results under different input representations while keeping the spatial graph fixed. Relative to the baseline model using infection rates only, incorporating raw socioeconomic variables or learned node embeddings is associated with lower MAPE. However, both representations also produce higher MAE and RMSE on average, while R^2 remains largely unchanged across configurations. Taken together, these results suggest a tendency for additional node level information to be more helpful for relative error than for absolute error in Glasgow, although this pattern is modest and should be interpreted with caution. Figure 2 visualises the learned node embeddings for Glasgow. The 2D t-SNE projections do not show strong clustering by individual socioeconomic variables, whereas the 3D embedding exhibits a smoother and more continuous structure. This pattern is consistent with the idea that the embeddings may capture gradual spatial variation in socioeconomic context rather than sharply separated zone types.

1. <https://www.opendata.nhs.scot/dataset/covid-19-in-scotland>.

2. Urban Big Data Centre (UBDC): <https://data.ubdc.ac.uk/datasets/6d87635c-96bb-4b7a-9a2e-676bb250032d>.

3. <https://download.geofabrik.de/europe/united-kingdom/scotland.html>.

4. <https://www.gov.scot/collections/scottish-index-of-multiple-deprivation-2020/>.

Table 1: Forecasting performance under different input representations in Glasgow.

Input representation	MAE (/100k)	RMSE (/100k)	MAPE (%)	R^2
Baseline (infection rate only)	80.01	133.22	48.89	0.90
Raw features (baseline + socioeconomic variables)	82.34±1.07	143.97±2.73	47.21±0.23↓	0.90±0.01
Node embedding (embedding replaces raw variables)	83.30±1.26	150.67±1.10	44.65±2.50↓	0.90±0.01

Note: Results are reported as mean \pm standard deviation over 5 independent runs with different random seeds. The spatial graph is fixed to the configuration selected by the baseline model. Lower values of MAE, RMSE, and MAPE indicate better performance (\downarrow), while higher R^2 indicates improved goodness of fit (\uparrow).

Table 2: Forecasting performance under different input representations in Edinburgh.

Input representation	MAE (/100k)	RMSE (/100k)	MAPE (%)	R^2
Baseline (infection rate only)	78.24	146.92	43.81	0.88
Raw features (baseline + socioeconomic variables)	79.25±5.43	142.98±4.14↓	44.50±3.59	0.88±0.01
Node embedding (embedding replaces raw variables)	78.13±2.33↓	144.45±8.84↓	42.35±3.98↓	0.88±0.01

Note: Results are reported as mean \pm standard deviation over 5 independent runs with different random seeds. The spatial graph is fixed to the configuration selected by the baseline model. Lower values of MAE, RMSE, and MAPE indicate better performance (\downarrow), while higher R^2 indicates improved goodness of fit (\uparrow).

Figure 2: t-SNE visualisations of learned node embeddings (Glasgow).

3.2 Edinburgh

For Edinburgh, spatial interactions are represented using geographic adjacency. As shown in Table 2, incorporating learned node embeddings yields the strongest average performance among the three input configurations, with lower MAE, RMSE, and MAPE than the infection only baseline. In contrast, raw socioeconomic features improve RMSE on average but do not show consistent gains in MAE or MAPE. Overall, the Edinburgh results suggest that learned node embeddings provide a more effective representation of area level socioeconomic context than the direct use of

raw socioeconomic variables in this setting.

The 2D t-SNE projection in Figure 3 shows a structured, non random organisation of nodes with smooth socioeconomic gradients, while clearer clustering patterns emerge in the 3D embedding space. This visual pattern suggests that node embeddings may capture latent socioeconomic heterogeneity more effectively when higher dimensional structure is preserved.

Figure 3: t-SNE visualisations of learned node embeddings (Edinburgh).

4. Conclusion and Future work

This study builds on our previous work on link-level spatial heterogeneity by examining whether node-level socioeconomic representations further enhance GNN-based epidemic forecasting. We find that while node embeddings improve MAPE in Glasgow but not absolute error, they improve both relative and absolute error in Edinburgh. This indicates that the effectiveness of node embeddings depends on how socioeconomic heterogeneity aligns with the dominant spatial interaction structure. In mobility-dominated cities such as Glasgow, absolute error metrics are largely driven by short-term outbreak peaks, which are less influenced by static socioeconomic attributes, limiting the impact of embeddings. In contrast, in cities with more locally structured transmission patterns such as Edinburgh, socioeconomic context aligns more closely with case distribution, allowing improvements across metrics. The divergence between relative and absolute error can be explained by the interaction between low-incidence zones, temporal peaks, and spatial heterogeneity in case counts. Node embeddings primarily stabilise predictions in low- and medium-incidence areas, improving MAPE, while high-incidence zones and peak dynamics continue to dominate MAE and RMSE in mobility-driven settings.

Overall, these findings highlight that neither link-level nor node-level representations are universally optimal, underscoring the need for context-aware GeoAI models. We adopt a two-stage learning strategy to isolate node-level socioeconomic effects under fixed spatial interaction structures. While our analysis focuses on two cities, future work will extend this framework to additional

urban contexts to assess whether the observed city-dependent behaviour reflects general principles of epidemic dynamics rather than isolated cases. The datasets used in this study are available from the cited sources. The code is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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